

IJMSBR

<https://www.ijmsbr.com/>

Impact Factor: 6.049

Life Cycle Costing and Firms' Performance: Evidences from Quoted Financial Institutions in Nigeria

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾**MADU Ikemefuna**-Department of Business Administration, Federal University Gashua, Yobe State. E-Mail: mriyke3@gmail.com ⁽²⁾**Sunday Alewo Omale Ph.D**-Department of Business Administration, Federal University Gashua, Yobe State. E-Mail: drsaomale@gmail.com ⁽³⁾**ATTAH Eleojo Vincent Ph.D**-Department of Banking and Finance, Veritas University, Abuja. E-Mail: attah@veritas.edu.ng

Abstract

Life cycle cost methods informs the management if the entire cost to be incurred on a product or project can be fully recovered and at when due with a substantial profit to be realized. Objectively, the study determines the effect of return on investment (ROI) on the performance of listed companies in Nigeria. An ex-post factor research design was used while the population consists of all the fifty-three (53) companies in the financial sectors quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange for eight (8) years period from 2013-2020. The sample size comprises of 27 companies in the financial sector which comprises of Banking and Insurance that are quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The study employed Robust Fixed Effect Regression Model because it's effective in the estimation of panel data after conducting some diagnostic tests. The finding is in line with the priori expectation of the researcher and also with the Miller and Modigliani Based on the assumption of a perfect capital market. It concludes and recommends that Management of companies should have a policy for adequate return on equity to attract more investments from the equity investors into the firms.

Key Words: Financial Institution, Life cycle costing and Return on investment.

Introduction

In today's world, life cycle costing (LCC) is widely applicable to new product development, project evaluation, and equipment procurement and maintenance. It is used to determine the entire cost to be incurred on a product or project right from the planning, research, and development stages up to when customer service is withdrawn (Dell'Isola and Kirk, 2003). LCC is defined in the literature as the procedure followed in recognising and recording the overall costs entailed over the life of an asset of the firm (Bierer, Götze, Meynerts and Sygulla, 2015). LCC is a branch of Whole Life Costing (WLC) where WLC is defined as a systematic consideration of all relevant costs and revenues associated with the acquisition of an asset over a period of analysis as defined in the agreed scope (BS ISO 15686, 2017 in Manewa, Siriwardena and Wijekoon, 2021). In this circumstance, unless there is an assurance that the entire production costs are incurred up to when customer services were withdrawn can be fully recovered before imitators bring out their identical products (Iwarere, 2009). To invest in any product development project or any new product production, the company has to find out its technology stage in the life cycle. When the company is implementing any new technology, platform or even new product based on new technology should recognize if the technology is growing or disappearing to other trade-offs by technology future (Gao, Porter, Wang, Fang, Zhang, Wang and Huang, 2013), mostly the S-curve of the technology life cycle is based on Technology performance over time or cumulative development activities (Gao, et al., 2013).

Firms create competitive advantages using their knowledge, skills, chains and processes to create superior products at lower prices. In such a competitive environment, efficient maintenance methods can mean the difference between a thriving profitable firm and one that losses money and sales. Maintenance can effect

product quality, capital costs, labor costs, and even inventory costs amounting to efficiency losses to both the producer and consumer (Douglas, 2018). Investors are looking for opportunities to invest additional resources in the most efficient capital markets and one of the main factors that every investor has in making his/her decision is to give special attention to stocks price. One of the most common ways of assessing the relative values of stock among practitioners is to compare the numbers listed in financial statements by using financial ratios. DeWet and DuToit (2007), noted that over the years, several performance measures have been used on the assumption of having some correlation with shareholder value. Financial managers, analysts and researchers have thought that the value of a company can be determined by using traditional accounting measures of performance expressed as financial ratios. These ratios include return on assets, return on equities and returned on capital employed among others.

Operating an efficient and cost-effective manufacturing process with strict control of material and production costs is the goal of every successful company, Nigerian companies inclusive. When coupled with the typically slim profit margins of manufacturers, these process changes represent a major capital investment to a company and emphasize the importance of selecting an efficient, cost-effective process that will allow the company to remain competitive (Innocent and Chimezie, 2013).

Statement of the Problem

Vital problems affecting the life cycle costing and financial firm performance include but are not limited to declining of life cycle of many products as a result to rapid changes in technology and high level of imitators who are out waiting for new product and copy to stereotype, inadequate raw materials and inventory shortages, obsolete equipments and equipments breakdown in the financial institution, lack of man power to operate new machines and as such, create room for constant staff training which will increase running cost. Inflationary pressure, inability to meet the budget target, supply chain challenges, infrastructural challenges such as poor road network, inadequate public power supply, lack of maintenance of equipment and machinery equally constitute problems of financial firms in Nigeria. However, the financial institutions own duty to the general public to fully disclose matters concerning strengths, weaknesses and prospects of their operations to aid in making investment decisions because information obtained from its financial reports are used to predict future investment. In view of these problems, the objective of the studies is not farfetched.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the effects of Life Cycle Costing and Performance of Quoted financial firms in Nigeria. Specifically, the study objective is to determine the effect of return on investment (ROI) on the performance of listed companies in Nigeria.

H_{a1}: Return on Investment (ROI) has no significant effect on the performance of listed companies in Nigeria.

Review of Literature

Conceptual Framework

Three proxies adopted to conceptualize this study are Return on Asset (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE) and Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) which decomposes the independent variable (Return on Investment) and proxy by (Firm Performance) as a dependent variable.

Source: Researchers Conceptualization

Life Cycle Costing (LCC)

LCC was introduced by top management with the help of researchers because of such an identified rupture; the extant routines are not centred on offering product as a service but rather on the sale of products. LCC was introduced at IpsosCo as a practice and this whole research focused on addressing how this practice contested and conformed to extant practices (Kambanou, 2020). Life Cycle Costing (LCC) has been established as a mechanism to help asset managers in decision making processes and to accomplish an assessment of the life cycle costs of selected assets of the firm (De Luca, Molari, Seddaiu, Toscano, Bombino, Ledda, Milani and Vittuari, 2015). LCC refers to the “cost management method for the evaluation of all economic consequences (e.g., costs, revenues, cash flows) and monetary tradeoffs occurring in an object's life cycle” (Bierer, Götze, Meynerts and Sygulla, 2015). The costs associated with LCC are the total costs of all the activities accomplished by the firm and this includes, amongst others, the supply of components and disposal of packaging (Kozarkiewicz and Lada, 2014).

The LCC is a useful technique for improving the capital investments of assets of the firm (Iotti and Bonazzi, 2014). LCC is mainly perceived in literature to predict cash flows and to provide an option appraisal, whilst allowing for the monitoring of costs and calculations of predicted future operational costs to an asset (Kelly and Hunter, 2009). The process involves the development of a plan, selection of LCC model, implementation of LCC model, recording and reviewing the results (Stanford University, 2005). LCC integrates several mathematical calculations that help to identify the future costs (Flanagan, Jewell and Norman, 2005). The methods, Annual Equivalent Cost; Net Present Value; Payback Method; Net Savings; Internal Rate of Return and Savings to Investment Ratio are quite common methods that are used within LCC (RICS, 2016 in Manewa, Siriwardena and Wijekoon, 2021).

Financial Performance

Kenton (2019), reviewed that financial performance is a subjective measure of how well a firm can use assets from its primary mode of business and generate revenues. Geber (2018), list out variances between actual revenues or expenses and budgeted revenues or expenses, operating cash flow, working capital, current ratio, debt to equity ratio, accounts payable turnover, accounts receivable turnover, inventory turnover, return on equity, quick ratio, and customer satisfaction as key indicators to track in ascertaining financial performance. Other measures used to measure financial performance by other researchers include Returns on Equity (ROE), Returns on invested capital, Return on Assets (ROA). Marshall (2019), writes that ROA is best used when comparing a company's past and present performance or when comparing companies in the same sector since, unlike ROE.

An appropriate application of the LCC had enabled firms to increase investments, and ensuring enhanced business efficiency and decreased manufacturing costs (Mbhazima, 2021).

This leads to maximisation of firm profitability and performance (Iotti and Bonazzi, 2014). The LCC has been regarded as a valuable and systematic technique for the inception and management of the investments (Mbhazima, 2021). Kozarkiewicz and Lada (2014), argues that “the life cycle costing is an exemplary tool of strategic project management accounting which develops the scope of analysis and cost measurement outside the frames of organisation realising the project: depending on the adopted perspective of making such costing it includes costs incurred by manufacturers of materials or subassemblies, or costs incurred by customers due to the purchase, utilisation and disposal of project's product”.

Several measurements of firm performance are used as indices of performance of the management and performance of the board of directors and the main signal for a corporate investment decision. This measure of performance is either the accounting measure or the market measure of firm performance (Downen, 2001; Haniffa and Hudaib, 2006). The accounting measure of performance is Return on Asset (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE), and Return on Investments (ROI) which is indicated by market profit margin on Sale and Earning per Share (EPS). The firm earnings and the profit for the year are measured from the amount of capital contributed to the running of the business. The higher the result, the more efficient the management of Assets is (Gitman and Vandenberg, 2000). This method of measurement is based on the financial information of the company of historical results. This includes operating earnings, revenue and profit.

Theoretical Framework

Theories of Dividend Policy and Signalling Hypothesis

Miller and Modigliani originally proposed their seminal irrelevance proposition in 1958. Based on the assumption of a perfect capital market, they concluded that dividend policy is irrelevant to shareholders or any other rational investor (Yousef, Patra and Tanna, 2016). They further proposed that the value of a firm should depend only on its investment opportunities (i.e, investment in positive NPV projects) and that financial decisions should be separate from investment decisions. A host of studies over several decades have tested the irrelevance proposition (Richardson, Sefik and Thompson, 1986; DeAngelo, DeAngelo and Stulz, 2006), but the results of such studies have tended to contradict the theory, and dividends continue to be perceived positively by capital markets. Lintner's (1956), most firms have aimed to set and maintain a steady dividend policy, and from both the perspectives of insider managers and outsider investors, a steady payout policy is generally perceived as good news. These empirical observations are thus consistent with the signalling theory of dividends or its variants (Yousef, Patra and Tanna, 2016).

Bhattacharya (1979), Leary and Michaely (2011), both theoretical and empirical studies maintain that if dividend payouts are sufficiently costly, they can be used as signals to solve the well-known "lemons problem" (Akerlof, 1970). Costs are thus very important in signalling theory: due to various dissipative costs associated with dividend payouts, firms with low earning potential will be unable to maintain steady dividend payouts. Further empirical evidence supporting the signalling hypothesis is provided by Miller and Rock (1985), John and Williams (1985), and Goddard, McMillan and Wilson (2006).

Empirical Review

Mbhazima, (2021), researched on the integrating environmental costs into asset life cycle costing and acquisition strategy. The paper argues that effective LCC and life cycle assessment (LCA) are fundamental to the attainment of the firm's long term goals and enhances organisational performance. The method applied in the study is a normative research approach, where the researcher has presented and illustrated the existing life cycle costing approach and illustrated further how environmental costs can be integrated to broaden the cost base to include environmental considerations. The study presents a Life Cycle Cost Assessment Framework. In conclusion, the study recommends that firms should administer and control their environmental issues and costs to improve performance.

Arkan (2016), investigates the importance of financial ratios derived from financial statements to predict stock price trends in emerging markets. A statistical examination of the prediction power of 12 financial ratios was tested depending on data of 15 companies distributed on 3 sectors for the years 2005-2014 in the Kuwait financial market. An equation to estimate the stock price in each sector was built according to the multiple OLS regression model after eliminating non-effective variables with the STEPWISE method. The results showed that some ratios could give strong positive and significant relationships to stock price behaviour and trends, the most effective ratios on the stock price for the industrial sector are ROA, ROE, and net profit ratio (NPR). Also, the most effective ratio on the stock price for the service sector was the ROA, ROE, P/E and EPS ratio and the same for the investment sector. The study recommended a set of financial ratios for each sector to predict stock price. The study used a weaker statistical tool of ordinary least square regression technique to estimate the panel data as against the postulate of Hausman (1978). The study was equally carried out in another environment outside Nigeria in the past which cannot be generalized because of the environmental differences and also the need to update the study up to the current period in Nigeria.

Olabisi and Dafe (2014), studied on the implementation of target costing in small and medium scale businesses in Nigeria. The study was a cross-sectional survey in which primary data were obtained from the selected small and medium scale enterprises in the three senatorial districts of Ogun State, Nigeria. The study set out to ascertain the relationship that exists between target costing and turnover on one hand and target costing and profitability on the other hand. The results of the regression analysis carried out substantiate the fact that profit can be enhanced either by increasing the sales value or reducing the cost components of products or both concurrently.

Innocent and Chimezie (2013), Examined the principles of costing and cost analysis as a tool for production costs control: A case study of Nigerian Companies. Methods of recovery of overhead costs are also discussed together with depreciation accounting methods and rationalized equipment cost recovery techniques. The findings reviewed that the most crucial aspect of inventory cost in the Nigerian habitually

speculative industry is that the stored goods represent capital (money) which would have been yielding interest if invested in a bank but tied down as stock in the company. The framework of the study is based on the knowledge of mathematical, experience and practice, which is applied with judgment to develop the ways to utilize economically the materials and other natural resources for profit making purpose. The study would be of significant to the manager in terms of analytical decision making, inventory control policies and determination of the company's profit level.

Analytical Methodology and Related Statistics

An *ex-post* factor research design was used considering that the data used for the study is historic data available in a secondary form while the study population consists of all the fifty-three (53) companies in the financial sectors quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange for eight (8) years period from 2013-2020. The sample size of this study comprises of 27 companies in the financial sector which comprises of Banking and Insurance that are quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The companies were selected for the study via random sampling technique methods because all the companies in the financial sector quoted on the NSE has equal chances of being selected as they all have data over this period of study. Data were secondary sourced from the financial statements of the sampled companies for the various years under study. The study employed robust fixed effect regression model because it's effective in the estimation of panel data after conducting some diagnostic tests. The analysis was carried out with the aid of STATA 15 software.

Model Specification

The dependent variable of this study is firm performance (FP) while the independent variable is Life Cycle Costing which is decompose as Return on Investment (ROI) and measured by Return on Assets (ROA); Return on Equity (ROE); Return on Capital Employed (ROCE).

In econometric terms, the model is represented as;

$$FP = \beta_0 + \beta_1ROA_{it} + \beta_2ROE_{it} + \beta_3ROCE_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

Where;

FP = Indicator representing Firm Performance

β_0 = a constant;

β_{1-3} = coefficients of independent variables;

ROA = Return on Asset;

ROE = Return on Equity;

ROCE = Return on Capital Employed;

μ = Stochastic error term;

i = Firms;

t = Period;

f = Functional Relationship.

Data Presentation and Analysis

The data of twenty-seven (27) financial firms regarding the firm performance (FP), Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE) and Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) are used for the analysis. The data were analysed with the aid of STATA 15 software using Descriptive Statistics, Shapiro-Wilk Test, Pearson Correlation, Heteroscedasticity test, Hausman Specification Test and Robust Random Effect Regression Model.

Descriptive Statistics

Summary of the descriptive statistics of the entire data set.

Variable	Observation	Mean	Standard Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
FP	216	3.883935	6.928639	.2	34.45
ROA	209	1.835018	4.407055	-26.95	18.45
ROE	209	5.414929	11.12984	-60.88	35.79
ROCE	209	5.656843	11.60712	-60.88	50.75

Source: Researcher's Computation using STATA 15 Software

Table 1 shows that the firm performance (FP) has a minimum value of 0.2, a maximum value of 34.45 and a mean value of 3.883935 that is within the minimum and maximum values indicating a good spread within the period of study. The table also reveals that FP has a standard deviation of 6.928639 that is more than the mean, which implies that it had strong growth for the period under review. It also reviewed that Return on Assets (ROA) has a minimum value of 26.95, maximum value of 18.45 and mean value of 1.835018 that is within the minimum and maximum indicating a good spread within the period of study. It also reviewed that ROA has a standard deviation of 4.407055 that is more than the mean, which implies that it had strong growth during the period under review. The table also reviewed that the Return on Equity (ROE) has a minimum value of -60.88, maximum value of 35.79 and a mean value of 5.414929 that is within the minimum and maximum values indicating a good spread within the period of study. The table also revealed that ROE has a standard deviation of 11.12984 that is more than the mean, which implies that it had a strong growth for the period under review. The table further review that Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) has a minimum value of -60.88, Maximum value of 50.75 and a mean value of 5.656843 that is within the minimum and maximum indicating a good spread within the period of study. It also revealed that ROCE has a standard deviation of 11.60712 that is more than the mean, which implies that it had strong growth during the period of review.

Shapiro-Wilk Test for Normality Results

Variable	Observation	W	V	Z	Prob. Chi ²
FP	216	0.57499	67.808	9.740	0.00
ROA	209	0.79086	32.421	8.022	0.00
ROE	209	0.72292	42.952	8.671	0.00
ROCE	209	0.72215	43.073	8.677	0.00

Source: *Researcher’s Computation using STATA 15 Software*

The above table shows the probability values of all the variables i.e the firm performance (FP), Return on Assets (ROA), Return on Equity (ROE) and Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) are not normally distributed around their mean values. This indicates that one of the basic assumptions of the linear regression technique is violated.

Pearson Correlation

Pearson Correlation matrix showing the extent of Associations between the variables

Variable	FP	ROA	ROE	ROCE
FP	1			
ROA	0.5243	1		
ROE	0.8442	0.5655	1	
ROCE	0.2240	-0.0087	0.0816	1

Source: *Researcher’s Computation using STATA 15 Software*

The result from the above table shows that 52.4% has positive and moderate relationship between Return on Assets (ROS) and firms performance (FP) of quoted financial firms in Nigeria from the correlation coefficient of 0.5243 at 1% level of significance (p-value 0.0000). The table also shows that 84% has positive and strong relationships between return on equity (ROE) and firms performance (FP) of quoted financial firms in Nigeria, while the correlation coefficient of 0.8442 is significant at 1% level of significance and with (p-value 0.0000). Finally, 11% shows positive and weak relationships between Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) and firms’ performance (FP) of quoted financial firms in Nigeria from the correlation coefficient of 0.1140 which has significant at 1% level of Significance (p-value 0.0000). However, the relationship between proxies of independent variable suggest being mild as all coefficients are below the threshold of 0.80 as suggested by (Gujarati, 2003).

Heteroscedasticity test

Type of test	Chi ²	P-Value
Heteroscedasticity test	14.29	0.0002

Source: *Researcher’s Computation using STATA 15 Software*

To authenticate that the study use a robust model, heteroscedasticity test was carried out. At the end, the study revealed that data is heteroskedastic; hence, the basic linear regression model would not be reliable. As it fails to satisfy the classical linear regression assumption of homoskedasticity (constant error variance).

Hausman Specification Test

Chi ²	487.19
Prob. Chi ²	0.00

Source: *Researcher's Computation using STATA 15 Software*

This study uses the panel data which can lead to an error that is clustered and possibly correlated over time. This is because each financial firm may have its entity-specific characteristic that can determine its information (Unobserved heterogeneity) this may also bias the outcome variable or even the explanatory variables. Hausman test shows that the fixed affect model is more appropriate.

Life Cycle Costing and Firm Performance Using Robust Fixed Effect Model (FEM)

Variable	Coefficients	t-value	Prob.
Cons.	-62.75918	-7.39	0.0000
ROA	0.29962	0.90	0.367
ROE	.2604473	20.89	0.000
ROCE	2269.507	6.10	0.000
Rs Overall	0.7188		
Wald chi	555.12		
Prob. > Chi ²	0.000		

Source: *Researcher's Computation using STATA 15 Software*

The above results indicates that 72% variation of firms performance (FP) is predicted by the combined effect of return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROQ) and return on capital employed (ROCE) with overall P-sq of 0.7188). This indicates that the model of the study is fit and the independent variables are properly combined and used. The wald chi² value of 555.12 with a P-value of 0.00 signified that the model is fit for the study.

Test of Hypothesis

H_{a1}: Return on Investment (ROI) has no significant effect on the performance of listed companies in Nigeria.

The z-value of 6.10 and the corresponding p-value of 0.000 shows that Return on Capital Employed (Return on Investment) has a significant positive effect on firms performance (FP) of listed companies in Nigeria for the period under review, Based on this, the null hypothesis which says that Return on Investment has no significant effect on the performance of listed companies in Nigeria is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

This study reveals that Return on Investment (ROI) has a significant positive effect on firms performance (FP) of quoted financial firms in Nigeria for the period under review. This implies that N1 increase in return on investment (ROI) will increase the firm's performance (FP) of quoted financial firms in Nigeria by 2269.507. This finding is in line with the priori expectation of the researcher because return on investment significantly enhances the firm's performance of listed companies in Nigeria. The findings is also in line with the Miller and Modigliani Based on the assumption of a perfect capital market, they concluded that dividend policy is irrelevant to shareholders or any other rational investor (Yousef, Patra and Tanna, 2016). They further proposed that the value of a firm should depend only on its investment opportunities (i.e, investment in positive NPV projects) and that financial decisions should be separate from investment decisions. In reality, companies that have a favourable return on investment will attract more equity investors which reflect their firms' performance. The return on investment (ROI) has a significant effect on the performance of listed companies in Nigeria for the period under review.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Companies with consistency and good policy on retaining earnings attract more investments from the equity investors into their organization hence, increasing the firms' financial performance. Based on this, the study recommended thus;

1. The financial firms should increase her level of retaining earnings as such that will attract equity investments in their firms.
2. Management of companies should have a policy for adequate return on equity to attract more investments from the equity investors into the firms.
3. Finally, tax holiday if given by government or host community should be retained into the business as it will enhance the company's capital.

Reference

- i. Akerlof, G.A. (1970). The market for lemons: quality uncertainty and the market mechanism. *Quart. J. Econ.* 84(1), 488-500.
- ii. Arkan, T. (2016). The importance of financial ratios in predicting stock price trends: A case study in emerging markets. *Finance, RynkiFinansowe, Ubezpieczenia nr 1(79)*, 13-26. DOI: 10.18276/frfu.2016.79-0.
- iii. Bhattacharya, S. (1979). Imperfect information, dividend policy, and 'the bird in the hand' Fallacy. *Bell J. Econ.* 10(1), 259-270.
- iv. Bierer, A., Götze, U., Meynerts, L. and Sygulla, R. (2015). Integrating life cycle costing and life cycle assessment using extended material flow cost accounting. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 108, Pp. 1289-1301.
- v. Douglas, M. (2018). Deciphering a Meal. In *Food and Culture* (Pp. 29-47). Routledge.
- vi. DeAngelo, H., DeAngelo, L. and Stulz, R. (2006). Dividend Policy and the Earned /contributed capital mix: a test of the life cycle theory. *J. Financ. Econ.* 81(2), 227-254.
- vii. Dell'Isola, A.J. and Kirk, S.J. (2003). Life cycle costing for facilities. New York: RSMMeans.
- viii. De Luca, A.I., Molari, G., Seddaiu, G., Toscano, A., Bombino, G., Ledda, L., Milani, M., and Vittuari, M. (2015). Multidisciplinary and Innovative Methodologies for Sustainable Management in Agricultural Systems. *Environmental Engineering and Management Journal*, 14(7), Pp. 1571-1581.
- ix. Dewet, J.H. and Dutoit, E. (2007). Return on equity: A popular, but flawed measure of corporate financial performance. *South African Journal of Business Management*, 38(1), 59-69.
- x. Downen, R. J. (2001). Fundamental information and monetary policy: The implications for earnings and earnings forecasts. *Journal of Business Finance & Accounting*, 28(3-4), 481-501.
- xi. Flanagan, R., Jewell, C. and Norman, G., (2005). Whole life appraisal for construction. Oxford: Blackwell Science.
- xii. Gao, L., Porter, A.L., Wang, J., Fang, S., Zhang, X., Ma, T., Wang, W. and Huang, L. (2013). *Technology Life Cycle Analysis Method based on Patent Documents*, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 80 (3), 398-407.
- xiii. Gerber, B. (2018). 12 Key Financial Performance Indicators You Should Be Tracking. (Online) <https://www.accountingdepartment.com/blog/12-key-performance-indicators-you-should-be-tracking>, last accessed 2019/11/03.
- xiv. Gitman, L. J. and Vandenberg, P. A. (2000). "Cost of Capital Techniques Used by Major US Firms: 1997 vs. 1980," *Financial Practice and Education*, Vol. 10, No. 2, Fall/Winter, 2000, Pp. 53-68.
- xv. Goddard, J., McMillan, D.G. and Wilson, J.O. (2006). Dividend smoothing vs dividend signalling: evidence from UK firms. *Manage. Finance* 32(6), 493-504.
- xvi. Haniffa, R. and Hudaib, M. (2006). Corporate governance structure and performance of Malaysian listed companies. *Journal of business finance & accounting*, 33(7-8), 1034-1062.
- xvii. Hargrave, M. (2019). Return on Equity-ROE. Retrieved from Investopedia: <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/r/returnonequity.asp>.
- xviii. Hausman, J. A. (1978). Specification tests in econometrics. *Econometrica: Journal of the econometric society*, 1251-1271.

- xix. Innocent, N. and Chimezie, N. (2013). Principles of Costing and Cost Analysis as a tool for production Costs Control: A Case Study of Nigerian Companies. *Research Journal in Engineering and Applied Sciences*. 2(3):225-229. www.emergingresource.org (ISSN:2276-8467).
- xx. Iotti, M. and Bonazzi, G. (2014). The application of Life Cycle Cost (LCC) approach to quality food production: A comparative analysis in the Parma PDO ham sector. *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 11(9):1492-1506.
- xxi. Iwarere, H.T. (2009). *Competitive Management Accounting*. 1st Edn., Bhoti International Publishing Ltd., Egbe.
- xxii. John, K. and Williams, J. (1985). Dividends dilution and taxes: a signalling equilibrium. *J. Finance* 40(4), 1053-1070.
- xxiii. Kambanou, M. L. (2020). Life cycle costing: understanding how it is practised and its relationship to life cycle management—a case study. *Sustainability*, 12(8), 3252.
- xxiv. Kelly, J. and Hunter, K. (2009). Life cycle costing of sustainable design. London: RICS.
- xxv. Kenton, W. (2019). Cash value added (CVA). <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/cva.asp>.
- xxvi. Kozarkiewicz, A. and Lada, M. (2014). Strategic management accounting as a source of information for value-driven project management. *Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 2(3): 186-190.
- xxvii. Leary, M. and Michaely, R. (2011). Determinants of dividend smoothing: empirical evidence. *Rev. Finance. Stud.* 24, 3197-3294.
- xxviii. Lintner, J. (1956). Distribution of incomes of corporations among dividends, retained earnings and taxes. *Am. Econ. Rev.* 46(2), 97-113.
- xxix. Manewa, A., Siriwardena, M. and Wijekoon, C. (2021). Life Cycle Costing in Construction: Current trends and emerging direction. In Sandanayake, Y.G., Gunatilake, S. and Waidyasekara, K.G.A.S. (eds). *Proceedings of the 9th World Construction Symposium, 9-10 July 2021, Sri Lanka*. (Online). Pp. 403-412. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31705/wcs.2021.35>. Available from: <https://ciobwcs.com/Papers>.
- xxx. Mbhazima, W. (2021). Integrating Environmental Costs into Asset Life Cycle Costing and Acquisition Strategy. *The Journal of Accounting and Management*, (1 (11)), 74-82.
- xxxi. Miller, M.H. and Rock, K. (1985). Dividends Policy under asymmetric information. *J. Finance* 40(4), 1031-1051.
- xxxii. Olabisi, J. and Dafe P.O. (2014). Implementing Target Costing in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises in Ogun Industrial Metropolis. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. Center for Promoting Ideas, USA www.ijhssnet.com vol. 4:8.
- xxxiii. Richardson, G., Sefcik, S.E. and Thompson, R. (1986). A test of dividend irrelevance using volume reactions to a change individual policy. *J. Financ. Econ.* 17(2), 313-333.
- xxxiv. Stanford University, (2005). Guidelines for life cycle cost analysis, [Online] Available from :https://sustainable.stanford.edu/sites/default/files/Guidelines_for_Life_Cycle_Cost_Analysis.pdf (Accessed on 19th May 2021).
- xxxv. Yousef, I., Patra, S. and Tanna, S. (2016). Signalling and Lifecycle Theories in the Banking Sectors of GCC Frontier Markets: An Empirical Assessment. In Andrikopoulos, P., Gregoriou, G. N. and Kallinterakis, V. (Eds.), *Handbook of Frontier Markets: Evidence from Middle East North Africa and International Comparative Studies* (2:49-63). Academic Press. <http://store.elsevier.com/product.jsp?isbn=9780128092002&requestid=396542>.

APPENDIX

LIST OF QUOTED FINANCIAL FIRMS AS AT 31st DECEMBER, 2020

S/N.	NAME
Banking	
1.	Access Bank
2.	Eco Bank
3.	Fidelity Bank
4.	Guarantee Trust Bank
5.	Jaiz Bank Plc
6.	Sterling Bank Plc
7.	Union Bank Plc
8.	United Bank of Africa
9.	Unity Bank Plc
10.	Wema Bank Plc
11.	Zenith Bank Plc
Insurance Carriers, Brokers and Services	
12.	Regency Alliance Insurance Company Plc.
13.	Unic Diversified Holding Plc
14.	African Alliance Insurance Plc
15.	Aiico Insurance Plc
16.	Continental Reinsurance Plc
17.	Corner Stone Insurance Plc
18.	Goldlink Insurance Plc
19.	Guinea Insurance Plc
20.	Consolidated Hallmark Insurance Plc
21.	International Energy Insurance Plc
22.	Lasaco Assurance Plc
23.	Law Union and Rock Insurance Plc
24.	Linkage Assurance Plc
25.	Mutual Benefit Assurance Plc
26.	Nem Insurance Plc
27.	Niger Insurance Plc
28.	Prestige Assurance Plc
29.	Sovereign Trust Insurance Plc
30.	Sunu Assurance Nigeria Plc
31.	Standard Alliance Insurance Plc
32.	Universal Insurance Plc
33.	Wapic Insurance Plc
34.	Axamansard Insurance Plc
Micro Finance Bank	
35.	Nigerian Police Micro Finance Bank
Mortgage Carriers, Brokers and Services	
36.	Resort Savings and Loans Plc
37.	Abbey Mortgage Bank Plc
38.	Aso Savings and Loans Plc
39.	Infinity Trust Mortgage Bank Plc
40.	Union Homes Savings and Loans Plc
Other Financial Institutions	
41.	Stanbic IBTC Holding Plc
42.	African Prudential Plc
43.	Custodian Investment Plc
44.	Deap Capital Management and Trust Plc
45.	Nigeria Energy Sector Fund
46.	FBN Holding Plc
47.	FCMB Group Plc
48.	Royal Exchange Plc
49.	United Capital Plc
50.	Staco Insurance Plc
51.	Omoluabi Mortgage Bank Plc
52.	Value Alliance Value Fund
53.	Veritas Capital

Sources: NSEFact book; Website (2020)